

COMMAND-LINE CARTOGRAPHIC DATA PROCESSING FOR GEOPHYSICAL PLOTTING OF RWANDA USING GMT AND R SCRIPTS

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Abstract. This paper presents a case of the script-based cartographic data processing by the Generic Mapping Tools (GMT) and R language for geophysical mapping. The study area is located in Rwanda, Africa, which is notable for complex geological setting due to its specific location within the East African Rift. The active continental zone of the East African Rift extending in western Rwanda has importance on seismicity of the country. It affects gravity anomaly and influences the distribution and shape of the geomorphological landforms, as reflected in the topography of Rwanda. The aim of this study is to apply the cartographic command-line techniques for mapping. The geophysical goal is to highlight the correlations between the distribution, depth and magnitudes of earthquakes, topography and geophysics. Visualizing the geophysical anomalies and topography for the morphometric setting of Rwanda's terrain supports geological monitoring. The data include the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO), Earth Gravitational Model of 2008 (EGM2008), satellite derived gravity and the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM). Nine new thematic maps on Rwanda are presented and evaluated to demonstrate the influence of the East African Ridge on regional distribution of the earthquakes and volcanos in Rwanda. The maps demonstrated accurate and effective mapping achieved due to the functionality of R and GMT scripts. A regional analysis shows that the distribution of the earthquakes and volcanoes is the highest in the western part of Rwanda and the lowest in the east proving the correlation of the active seismicity with the tectonic setting and geology of the country. The console-based scripts of R and GMT are presented with provided link to the author's GitHub repository with a full access to the codes.

Key words: Geophysics, shell script, cartography, GMT, R language, Africa.

1. INTRODUCTION

Geophysical and seismic studies require visualisation of the recent earthquake events according to their magnitude, focal depth and distribution of sources. However, such mapping presents difficulties, due to a variety of methods in cartographic data processing. Many Geographic Information System (GIS) exist nowadays. For instance, the most well known GIS software widely used in geosciences include the ArcGIS, MapINFO, Erdas Imagine, Environment for Visualizing Images (ENVI)

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distribution of earthquakes in Rwanda with notable increase of seismicity in the west of the country in the proximity of the Albertine Rift and Kivu Lake. Such phenomena correlated with the topography of the country have thereby been visualised using the advanced cartographic methods, as described in existing publications on seismicity in Rwanda and Lake Kivu [11–15].

The GIS methods often entail difficulties in data formatting, converting, exporting data, preparation of layouts and other manipulations with geospatial data. This is largely caused by different standards in various GIS which requires individual adjustments in each mapping case. Moreover, during seismic interpretation and mapping, one frequently encounters difficulties in collecting and converting data, processing tabular datasets (.xls to .ngdc or .gmt formats) and the like.

Although the Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology (IRIS) Consortium [16–18] have made large efforts in exploring the Earth's interior through the collection and distribution of seismographic data, processing and visualisation of these data require additional skills and mapping. This paper aims to contribute to such tasks by introducing the GMT and R scripting for geophysical, topographic and seismic mapping of Rwanda.

The script-based cartographic method of GMT presents an alternative to the menu-based traditional GIS approach. For instance, geophysical maps plotted using GMT scripts can be prepared using the templates of scripts which significantly automates the workflow and acquires more precision and aesthetics through the machine-made graphics [19–22]. As application of such tools as R or GMT requires certain methodology in coding that complicates its direct application and requires explanation, this paper presents example of coding with technical comments on usability.

Applying scripting approaches of R programming is possible not only for statistical analysis and tabular data processing [23, 24] but also for mapping geospatial data. Both GMT and R scripts can be prepared and written directly in the Xcode and then run from the RStudio (for R) or the GMT environments, which is convenient for mapping. A shortcoming inherent in the GMT and R approach, consists in the steep learning curve of scripting. This can be generally mastered using the existing documentation [25–27] or examples of papers on scripting cartography [28–30].

Notable for high seismicity and complex geologic setting caused by the location in the East African Rift, Rwanda has a varied topographic relief and compact spatial extent of the country. In such a way, it present an excellent target in an attempt to demonstrate geophysical mapping using scripting methodology by GMT and R. Although the majority of the earthquakes in Rwanda have been estimated at depths not exceeding 10 km according to IRIS, some selected events were recorded at deeper depths, such as 11 (earthquake in 2015, 37 km North of Cyangugu, Rwanda), selected events in the Kivu Lake including region of Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), *e.g.*, earthquakes at depth 33 km on 21 May and July 7, 1981, earth-

2. STUDY AREA

Rwanda is a country with diverse contrasting topography in its western and eastern segments. Marked by the active tectonic setting of the East African Rift stretching in its western part, Rwanda is largely affected by the contrasting geophysical setting marked by complex geologic evolution of the region. The East African Rift system is an extensional lithosphere zone on the continent with repetitive earthquakes and continuous seismic activity caused by the distribution of tectonic faults [31]. The location of the East African Rift is caused by the lithospheric weaknesses in this region. Rifting processes here strongly correlate with the activation of the boundary faults. These faults accommodate basin subsidence which results in strongly asymmetric geomorphology in this region [32].

Fig. 3 – Geoid model of Rwanda. Mapping: GMT. Source: author.

The East African Rift is the major tectonic feature of Rwanda extending in the North-South direction along its western border, controlling and largely affecting the seismicity of the country. The western part of the country is geographically located within the Albertine Rift Mountains which structurally belongs to the East African Rift. This part of Rwanda has the highest topographic elevations. The relief here is

mainly presented by the hills and mountain chains (1,500 to 2,500 m). Notable objects here include the Lake Kivu and the Ruzizi River, located on the border between Rwanda and DRC. The topographic elevations in the west are notably higher on the westernmost part of Rwanda where the altitude drops abruptly near the shores of the Lake Kivu and the Ruzizi River.

Besides unique geologic setting, the Albertine Rift is the most biodiverse area on the Earth. Thus, a special mark of the Albertine Rift region includes the African biodiversity hotspot and protected area of Rwanda – an ecoregion of tropical moist montane broadleaf forests with a unique environment. Being one of the Africa's most ecologically sensitive environment, it comprises 162 endemic terrestrial vertebrates and plants with threatened status included in the global Red List [33]. At the same time, current ecological problems in Rwanda include land conversion for settlement and agricultural purposes, afforestation of some agricultural lands, decrease of some areas of the national forests [34].

The eastern region of Rwanda has notably lower topographic heights, which gradually decrease eastwards. The landscapes of this area are presented by savannah, valleys, plains, small lakes and swamps. Among the other remarkable geographic features of Rwanda, one should mention the Lake Rweru – the origin of the Nile River. The central part of Rwanda is presented by the mixed types of the topography with dominating hills in its western district. These border the Albertine segment of the East African Rift. The northern part of the country is marked by the presence of the Virunga Mountains, which form a part of the volcanoes chain in the East Africa. This mountain range consists of the eight major volcanoes, mostly dormant ones.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. DATA

To achieve the best cartographic performance, seismic mapping and analysis of the earthquake frequency and repeatability based on IRIS must be combined using the high-resolution topographic and geophysical datasets. To achieve this goal, this study applied such data covering Rwanda. The topographic data were taken from the existing GEBCO grid with 15 arc-second resolution, *i.e.*, ca. 450 m [35, 36].

The topographic map of Rwanda is presented in Fig. 1. The earthquake events were derived from the IRIS database and plotted in Fig. 2. The Earth Gravitational Model as of EGM2008 presents the geoid model data [37]. The EGM2008 was used here as the latest available version standard product of National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency (NGA), presenting the geopotential model of the Earth derived as reference of the geoid WGS-84. The geoid data were applied for mapping Fig. 3.

The free-air gravity data in Faye's reduction (Fig. 4) and the vertical gravity (Fig. 5) are based on the satellite-derived data collected by the sensor on-board of

Chart of the World (DCW) layer:

```
'gmt psclip -R28.5/31/-3/-1 -JM6.5i Rwanda.txt -O -K >> $ps'.
```

The topographic isolines of interval at each 250 m were measured and interpolated by a 'grdcontour' module of the GMT:

```
'gmt grdcontour rw_relief.nc -R -J -C250 -Wthinest,darkbrown -O -K >>$ps'.
```

The colour legend was plotted by 'psscale' module using the following code:

```
'gmt psscale -Dg28.5/-3.2+w16.5c/0.15i+h+o0.3/0i+ml+e -R -J -Cpauline.cpt
-Bg500f50a500+1"Colormap: (...) [R=806/4360, H, C=RGB]"
-I0.2 -By+1m -O -K >> $ps'.
```

The geoid EGM2008 initial grid was converted into the GMT format by the following code: 'gmt grdconvert s45e00/w001001.adf geoid_RW.grd'.

The data extent was ascertained using the Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (GDAL): 'gdalinfo geoid_TZ.grd -stats'. The resulting data range was used for preparing and stretching color palette for exact diapason of data.

Converting the img file by the 'img2grd' module: 'gmt img2grd grav_27.1.img -R28.5/31/-3/-1 -Ggrav.grd -T1 -I1 -E -S0.1 -V'.

Extracting the subset of the file in img format using the coordinates (-R28.5/31/-3/-1) by the 'grdcut' module: 'gmt grdcut grav.grd -R28.5/31/-3/-1 -Grw_grav.nc'. Here the extraneous areas in the global file GEBCO were eliminated which enabled computer processing to be speeded up due to the smaller piece of the raster grid to process, which covered only the area of Rwanda.

Adding isolines by the 'grdcontour' module: 'gmt grdcontour rw_grav.nc -R -J -C10 -A20 -Wthinest -O -K >> \$ps'.

Formatting of the map grid was performed using the gmt set up:

```
'FORMAT_GEO_MAP=ddd:mm:ssF'.
```

A map frame was defined for all the maps: '--MAP_FRAME_AXES=WEsN'.

```
Defining the frequency of ticks on a cartographic grid: '-Bpxg1f0.5a0.25
-Bpyg1f0.5a0.25 -Bsxg1 -Bsyg1'
```

Font annotations were defined for each hierarchical level of the annotations (title, labels, subtitle), e.g.: '--FONT_ANNOT_PRIMARY=7p,0,black'.

Adding and styling grid by the 'psbasemap' module: 'gmt psbasemap -R -J -B+t"Free-air gravity anomaly for Rwanda" -O -K >> \$ps'.

Placement of texts on the map: 'gmt pstext -R -J -N -O -K -F+jTL+f10p,26,blue2+jLB >> \$ps << EOF 29.2 -1.95 Lake 29.2 -2.05 Kivu EOF', where 'EOF' signifies 'End Of File', i.e., the command refers to the expression placed between the double EOF symbols.

Placement of the GMT logo: 'gmt logo -Dx7.0/-3.1+o0.1i/0.1i+w2c -O -K >> \$ps'.

Converting final PostScript graphics to image file by the GhostScript as follows: 'gmt psconvert Grav_RW.ps -A0.5c -E720 -Tj -Z'.

The codes provided above illustrate the modular concept of the scripting approach of GMT. Its main approach is to split the tasks of mapping into the several sub-tasks executed by the lines of code. For this reason and logical functionality, the application of the GMT is widely used in geophysical mapping [39–41]. Specifically, it is used for processing and handling of large spatial heterogeneous datasets, for performing overlays, analyses and for general statistical modelling. Using GMT enables to produce effective visual plotting through the extended cartographic options using scripting methodology, as demonstrated in the sequence of the codes above.

3.3. SCRIPTING IN R

To determine the extent and values of elevations (Fig. 6) based on SRTM-90 DEM of Rwanda a combination of ‘raster’ [42] and ‘tmap’ [43] packages of R [44] in RStudio environment [45] was applied. The geomorphometric features (slope, aspect, hillshade and heights) were identified based on the functionality of raster package: ‘slope = terrain(alt, opt = "slope")’ for computing slope gradient (Fig. 7), ‘aspect = terrain(alt, opt = "aspect")’ for modelling compass aspect orientation of the Rwanda slopes (Fig. 8) and ‘hill = hillShade(slope, aspect, angle = 40, direction = 270)’ for modelling hill shade with artificial illumination using previously made slope and aspect (Fig. 9). The elevations (Fig. 6) were visualised using ‘plot(alt)’ function.

However, for a better cartographic performance, mapping was improved by using the ‘tmap’ library through applying a set of its functions. For example, to select the better colour palettes, this was achieved using a ‘tmaptools::palette_explorer()’, embedded in the ‘tmap’ package of R. The visualisation of the raster grid was done by the following code for the slope: `tm_raster(title = "Slope (0u00B0-90u00B0)", palette = "-Set1", style = "quantile", n = 10, breaks = c(5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90), legend.show = T, legend.hist = T, legend.hist.z = 0,)`. In this code, the steepness variations of the slope were estimated for the ten classes in the study area of Rwanda.

The computed aspects of the slopes in Rwanda were divided into eight classes, according to the geographic orientation of the West-East-South-North (WESN) and auxiliary combinations (SW-SE-NE-NW). The histogram is presented in Fig. 8 below the map. The code included the following commands: ‘`tm_raster(title = "Aspect", palette = "-Spectral", style = "quantile", n = 8, legend.show = T, legend.hist = T, legend.hist.z=0,)`’ and ‘`tm_compass(type = "rose", position=c("right", "top"), size = 7.0)`’ for compass placement.

Using the ‘*tm_graticules*’ the ticks were added on the maps in Figs. 6, 7, 8 and 9: `tm_graticules(ticks = T, lines = T, col = "azure3", lwd = 1, labels.size=1.0, labels.rot = c(15, 15), labels.col = "black")`. Final export of the re-

sulting graphics has been done using the following code snippet:

'tmap_save' function:

```
`tmap_save(map4, "Rwanda_Elevation.jpg", dpi = 300, height = 10)'
```

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 visualises the topography map of Rwanda based on the GEBCO/SRTM high-resolution dataset. The topography of Rwanda was visualised and estimated by comparing these results with the previous data. The results of the topographic data analysis shown variations from minimum at 806.098 m to maximum at 4359.250 m (East African Ridge) and a statistical evaluation shown mean at 1662.746 m and standard deviation (StdDev) at 358.125 m. The hydrological setting of Rwanda are presented by several lakes that should be briefly noted. The Rweru Lake on the border with Burundi shown very shallow bathymetry not exceeding 2 m. The Ihema Lake is another notable largest lake of Rwanda located on the east of the country on the border with Tanzania, within the marshland of the Kagera River.

Fig. 5 – Vertical free-air gravity (Faye's) map of Rwanda. Mapping: R. Source: author.

The Muhazi Lake located in the centre of the country is presented by the flooded valley, extending mostly in the EW direction, with numerous tributaries in a NS direction. The Kivu Lake is one of the African Great Lakes located on the west of the country on the border with DRC. Its topographic shape is mostly irregular. The lake bed is located in a rift valley of the East African Rift that is notable for slow tectonic movements being gradually pulled apart, which causes volcanic activity in the area. The Lake Kivu is a fresh water lake notable for the limnic gas eruptions of the dissolved carbon dioxide (CO₂) which was a subject to a series of studies. Lake Kivu is situated in the proximity to the sources of natural disasters: an active volcano on Mt. Nyiragongo, an active earthquake zone along the East African Ridge and other active volcanoes in the north of Rwanda.

Fig. 6 – DEM SRTM-90 elevation heights map of Rwanda. Mapping: R. Source: author.

Figure 2 of the seismicity in Rwandan demonstrates the epicentres and magnitudes of the earthquakes recorded in the IRIS database that have been visualised on a map. These are dominating in the central part of the East African Rift Valley according to the period 1977 to 2020. Approved by the previous studies [46], the location of the earthquakes is controlled by the location and extent of the East African Rift. Most of the earthquakes are situated on the faults which border the East African Rift with a few on faults which cross-sectioning the East African Rift. The analysis

of spatial distribution of the seismic events and estimation of the geomorphometric results indicate that the earthquakes and eruptions in Rwanda occurred dominantly in the proximity of the Albertine Rift, the western branch of the East African Rift.

Figure 3 shows the geoid model of Rwanda based on the EGM2008. The values of the geoid anomalies over the Rwanda have values from minimal -16 to maximal 0 with the distribution of data clearly visible in EW direction with the highest values in the mountain regions in the East African Rift segments. However, the general anomaly values of geoid in Rwanda are negative which is caused by the regional differences in the Earth's gravity field caused by variations in the mass distribution and rock densities in the lithosphere.

Fig. 7 – Slope model map of Rwanda. Mapping: R. Source: author.

Figures 4 and 5 demonstrate the geophysical data distribution of Rwanda based on the satellite derived gravity anomaly fields. Figure 4 shows the free-air gravity (Faye's) map of Rwanda which shows measured gravity anomaly after a free-air correction applied to correct the elevation of the measurements. The analysis of Fig. 4 shows the following data distribution: Minimum=-73.067 mGal, Maximum=294.432 mGal, Mean=42.140 mGal, StdDev=45.560 mGal. Here the highest values are notable on the E and NE borders of the Lake Kivu (over 200 mGal, orange to red colours

in Fig. 4) while the lowest values (-20 mGal, blue colours in Fig. 4) are recorded in the east of the country. The Cyangugu region has values of around +20 mGal.

Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of the values of vertical free-air gravity model of Rwanda. Specifically, the data extent retrieved by the GDAL (`gdalinfo -stats rw_grav_v.nc`) shown that the minimum is -199.742 mGal, the maximum is 418.269 mGal, the mean is 5.492 and the standard deviation (StdDev) is 51.828 mGal. The comparison of these data with the free-air gravity shows vertical correction which results in a wider amplitude of data distribution according to the coefficient applied in the algorithm of gravity data computation for vertical gravity anomaly. Similar to the free-air gravity field, the vertical gravity demonstrates the highest values notable along the eastern border of the Kivu Lake (*i.e.*, the western region of Rwanda) where the values exceed 150 mGal. Likewise, the lowest values are notable in the eastern region of the country (0 to -25 mGal, yellow colours in Fig. 5) and very low values in local depressions: selected spots in Lake Kivu, Lake Burera in the north of Rwanda with values -150 (blue colours in Fig. 5).

Fig. 8 – Aspect model map of Rwanda. Mapping: R. Source: author.

Figures 6, 7, 8 and 9 demonstrate the series of the geomorphometric maps of Rwanda showing the derivatives of the elevation DEM analysis of Rwanda. The R

package 'raster' was used to calculate three important geomorphometric variables – slope gradient, aspect of terrain of Rwanda and hillshade highlighting vertical dissection of the relief. Figure 6 shows the elevation heights map of Rwanda based on the DEM SRTM-90. Figure 7 shows slope model map of Rwanda. Variations in the slope gradient clearly show the distribution of steep (red colours in Fig. 7) to moderate and low slopes over study area (beige and khaki colours in Fig. 7) in percentage (20%, 40%, 60% as large intervals of data distribution). Figure 8 shows the aspect model map of Rwanda. Here the interfluves of lakes and rivers of the country with dominant soil and morphologic processes and underlying geologic rock properties (porosity, density, lithology types) cause variations in aspect orientation. This is due to the local vertical soil–water movements and external exogenous effects, such as wind and solar factors causing soil erosion that affects the geomorphology of the terrain.

Fig. 9 – Hillshade visualization map of Rwanda. Mapping: R. Source: author.

Figure 9 shows the hillshade visualisation map of Rwanda with artificial illumination of the light source modeled using previously calculated slope and aspect based on the SRTM DEM 90 of Rwanda. The hillshade gradient was derived using a standard R algorithm of the geomorphometric modeling, then visualised using the

'tmap' package. The comparative analysis of the geomorphometric maps of Rwanda was also tested by visual overlay of the map series presented in the same projection and identical spatial extent. The hillshade illustrating vertical dissection of the terrain of Rwanda was mapped using the R scripts as deviation of the elevation, slope and aspect, as presented in Fig. 9.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The identification of active seismicity, earthquakes and volcanoes in Rwanda is of utmost importance not only for the Earth sciences (geology, tectonics and volcanology) but also for social aspects of risk disasters. The latter include prevention and prognosis of hazards, risk, assessment, evaluation of impact caused by the seismic events, analysis of the magnitude and locations of the earthquakes. For these reasons, selecting the advanced cartographic methods and optimal software for effective data processing mapping and visualisation is a challenging task. Selecting the most functional tool may help to choose the best methods from a variety of the existing applications in geosciences and geology [47–55].

A method for the precise and effective script-based mapping using GMT and R is proposed in this paper with a case of Rwanda. The main goal was to visualise the seismicity in the East African Rift region in comparison with the geophysical and topographic setting. The volcanic eruptions and earthquakes in Rwanda were ascertained and visualised using the IRIS dataset for 1977 to 2020, topographic mapping based on the GEBCO grid, geodetic and geophysical data (geoid and gravity grids) in comparison with the geomorphometric models of the terrain relief derivatives (slopes, aspect, hillshade and DEM). The comparison of scripting approaches of GMT and R, demonstrated in this paper, with conventional GIS methods of mapping can suggest the following advantages:

1. increased speed and precision of mapping due to the automated workflow and repeatability of scripts;
2. improved cartographic functionality due to the extended possibilities of GMT: adjustment of projections, variability of modules, etc.;
3. improved aesthetics of maps: fine tuning of design, a wide variety of colour palettes, visualisation elements: lines, objects, translucency of layers;
4. integrated data processing due to the compatibility with GDAL and extended list of the applicable raster and vector data formats.

Although data can be generally mapped using traditional GIS with a good accuracy [56–58], mapping workflow in GIS cannot be completely automated as much

as in GMT. This is because the individual layouts in GIS should be prepared manually for each map, which necessarily requires additional data processing. In contrast, scripting enables reuse of scripts run from the command line from a console, which significantly automates mapping procedure. Ascertaining the correlation between the seismicity in Rwanda, topography, geophysical geoid and gravity anomalies fields was possible using scripting GMT and R methods of the script-based mapping. In such a way, the paper applied the advanced methods of mapping for processing high-resolution reliable data to demonstrate the association of geology and seismicity with geophysical and topographic setting of Rwanda.

The automated data processing and statistical models are widely used in geosciences [59–64]. These and other papers concern many research questions about the effective data visualisation and modelling, data comparison and correlation, while mapping and cartographic plotting remain to be addressed. The presented scripting approach of GMT and R proposes the extension of the visualisation concepts to the geophysical and seismic maps. For example, these include the replicability of demonstrated scripts using the template for gravity and geoid models. Using scripts increases the speed and quality and precision of the geospatial data processing.

The questions of cartographic techniques raised in this paper contributed to the development of mapping approaches by demonstrating specific issues of scripting approaches to geospatial data processing, using a variety of GMT modules and R functions for data visualisation and mapping. Besides, this paper continues the existing studies on East Africa in general and Rwanda in particular through the demonstrated geophysical and seismic analysis of this region. The cartographic techniques demonstrated in this paper include, among others, the design of symbols and map layouts, location and placements of cartographic elements, presenting different thematic overlays to assess correlation between the seismic, geophysical and topographic setting in Rwanda, determining optimal colour palettes that are more suitable for depicting continuous geophysical and topographic data and discrete scatterplot seismic data, analysis of the data reliability, actuality and quality.

Besides, the comparison of the presented maps enables to better understand the topographic variability in the western and eastern parts of the country. Thus, print-quality illustrations and cartographic layouts contribute to a better understanding of the existing correlations between the geologic and geophysical phenomena of the East African Rift. The East Africa Rift, extending in the west of Rwanda, presents its western branch of the Albertine Rift, as shown in this study.

Finally, the visualised high-quality georeferenced reliable geoinformation on Rwanda helps not only in studies of the Earth science but also for environmental and sustainable development of the country by providing thematic maps. Besides, detailed maps of the topography and geologic setting may also be used in selected aspects of social studies of Rwanda: *e.g.*, risk assessment, seismic hazard prognosis

and social vulnerability of people at risks of earthquakes.

The existing GIS-based studies of Rwanda focused on geophysical mapping are restricted to the particular regions. They did not applied GMT and R based mapping of the multi-source datasets of DEM, geoid and gravity grids as thematic map series. Previous existing studies on Rwanda are not indicative of the correlation between the geophysical phenomena of Rwanda. In contrast, this study assessed the effectiveness of R and GMT methods in cartography for retrieving the high-resolution data of seismic, topographic and geophysical rasters on Rwanda. In this regards, this paper contributed to the extended multi-disciplinary studies of Rwanda environment, natural and Earth sciences. At the same time, it presented a new methodology of the cartographic data processing using script-based approach for cartographic data processing using a command line from the console.

6. LIST OF ACRONYMS

DCW Digital Chart of the World

DEM Digital Elevation Model

DRC Democratic Republic of the Congo

EGM2008 Earth Gravitational Model of 2008

ENVI Environment for Visualizing Images

GDAL Geospatial Data Abstraction Library

GEBCO General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans

GIS Geographic Information System

GMT Generic Mapping Tools

GRASS Geographic Resources Analysis Support System

IRIS Incorporated Research Institutions for Seismology

NGA National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency

QGIS Quantum GIS

SAGA System for Automated Geoscientific Analyses

SRTM Shuttle Radar Topography Mission

WESN West-East-South-North

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